

THE CONTRASTIVE ANALYSIS OF THE WAYS OF WORD-FORMATION IN ENGLISH AND TURKMEN

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Abstract: Ways of word-formation in English and Turkmen are analyzed in the article. Affixation, conversion and word-composition are the basic ways of creating new words in both languages. Issue of productivity of English and Turkmen derivational affixes is broadly discussed in this work. Word-forming activity of some English and Turkmen affixes is revealed.

Keywords: word-formation; affixation; conversion; word-composition; productive affixes; non-productive affixes; derivational affixes.

Introduction

In the Epoch of the Revival of the New Era of the Powerful State, by the great efforts of the National Leader of the Turkmen people our Hero-Arkadag and Highly Esteemed President our Motherland, independent and permanently neutral Turkmenistan develops day by day. There are many achievements in such spheres as policy, economy, industry, agriculture, science, education and culture. Special attention is paid to teaching foreign languages in our country.

The contrastive analysis of the non-related languages is also of great importance. Comparison of the phonetic, morphological, syntactical and lexical systems of the non-related languages gives opportunity to find out similarities and differences between them. The contrastive analysis of the English and Turkmen lexical systems assists the students to profoundly understand the English and Turkmen word-formation, word-structure, etymology of the English and Turkmen words and other aspects of lexicology.

Main Section

In both compared languages word-formation is the process of creating new words. A distinction is made between two principal types of word-formation: word-derivation and word-composition.

The basic ways of forming words in word-derivation are affixation and conversion. In both compared languages affixation is the formation of a new word with the help of affixes, e.g. *heart-less, over-do, king-dom, wonder-ful, warm-ly, dark-en, taryh-y, al-gy-dar, subut-nama, bar-la, göz-le* and etc. Words which consist of a root and an

affix (or several affixes) are called *derived words* or *derivatives* and are produced by the process of word-building known as *affixation* (or *derivation*) [Антрушина Г.Б., Афанасьева О.В., Морозова Н.Н. 1999, с. 79].

Conversion consists in making a new word from some existing word by changing the category of a part of speech: e.g. *fish – to fish, slave – to slave, to jump – jump, to peel – peel, bulamak, ýaşmak, süzme, üýşmek* and etc.

In English and Turkmen word-composition is the formation of a new word by combining two or more words, e.g. *door-handle, house-keeper, mother-in-law, notebook, textbook, düýedaban, atbakar, inedördül, orunbasar, milletara, günebakar, älemgoşar* and etc.

In both compared languages affixation is the most active way of word-formation. From the point of view of types of affixes, in English and Turkmen affixation is divided into **prefixation** and **suffixation**. There are many prefixes and suffixes in English, but there are only such prefixes in Turkmen as *bet-* (*bedasyl*), *bi-* (*biedep*), *nä-* (*näbelet*) and they are borrowed from Arabic and Persian.

In both compared languages there are productive and non-productive affixes. In English and Turkmen, the word-forming activity of affixes may change in the course of time. This raises the question of productivity of derivational affixes, i.e. the ability of being used to form new, occasional or potential words, which can be readily understood by the language-speakers. Thus, productive affixes are those used to form new words in the period in question. Some productive English and Turkmen suffixes are: 1) noun-forming suffixes: *-er* (*manager*), *-ing* (*fighting*), *-ness* (*sweetness*), *-ation* (*automation*), *-cy/-ci* (*okuwçy, işçi*), *-daş/-deş* (*obadaş, kârdeş*); 2) adjective-forming suffixes: *-able* (*tolerable*), *-ic* (*electronic*), *-ish* (*whitish*), *-ly/-li* (*akylly, bilimli*), *-syz/-siz* (*ynsapsyz, edepsiz*); 3) verb-forming suffixes: *-ize/-ise* (*vitaminize*), *-ate* (*oxidate*), *-la/-le* (*akla, sözle*), *-a/-e* (*suwa/süýje*).

The English adverb-forming suffix *-ly* (*equally*) is productive.

Non-productive affixes are the affixes which are not able to form new words in the period in question. Non-productive affixes are recognized as separate morphemes and possess clear-cut semantic characteristics. Some non-productive English and Turkmen suffixes are: 1) noun-forming suffixes: *-th* (*truth*), *-hood* (*sisterhood*), *-ship* (*scholarship*), *-c* (*igenç, dynç*), *-gyn* (*yangyn*); 2) adjective-forming suffixes: *-ful* (*peaceful*), *-some* (*tiresome*), *-en* (*golden*), *-ous* (*courageous*), *-gyn/-gin* (*gyzgyn, irgin*). The English verb-forming suffix *-en* (*strengthen*) is non-productive.

In Turkmen there are some non-productive suffixes which cannot be separated from the base; separation of these affixes from their base requires etymological analysis.

E.g. *pyçak, byçgy, tirsek, goltuk, içege* and etc.

The most productive prefixes in Modern English are: *de-* (*decontaminate*), *re-* (*rethink*), *pre-* (*prefabricate*), *non-* (*non-operational*), *un-* (*unfunny*), *anti-* (*antibiotic*).

There are some differences between the ways of word-formation in English and Turkmen. The main difference is in the classification of derivational affixes in Turkmen. There are simple and complex derivational affixes in Turkmen. In Turkmen

word-forming affixes can be divided into groups by structure, simple and complex. Examples of simple affixes include the derivational affixes *-çy*, *-çi*, *-la*, *-le*, *-gy*, *-gi*, *-ak*, *-ek*, *-g*, *-yk*, *-ik* in such words as *aw-çy*, *iş-çi*, *bar-la*, *iş-le*, *al-gy*, *ser-gi*, *or-ak*, *döw-ek*, *barla-g*, *ide-g*, *ýan-yk*, *äd-ik*, *döw-uk*. Complex affixes are usually formed as a result of a combination of two or more simple derivational affixes and word-forming actions occur only in this complex form. An example of this is the affix *-çylyk*, *-çilik*: *maldar-çylyk*, *guda-çylyk*, *dayhançylyk*, *arzan-çylyk*, *köp-çülik*, *az-çylyk*, *kem-çilik* and etc.

There are also **regular** and **irregular derivational affixes** in Turkmen. Although regularity and irregularity are related to the productivity or inefficiency of word-forming affixes, they are not mutually exclusive phenomena. Derivational affixes are not equal in their participation in the formation of lexical units.

Regular affixes participate in the word-formation from a large number of words and are able to form words with a stable lexical meaning. In such lexical units, the derivational affix has a pattern of generating a certain group of lexical words in the semantic relationship between the word-former and the derivative word. Consequently, the meaning of the affix is also known outside of the specific added word, and it is not difficult to divide the derivative word into morphemes that have an independent semantic meaning. For example, it is well known that the affixes *-çy*, *-çi* form nouns that mean a person engaged in some profession or activity, the affixes *-ly*, *-li* mean presence, and *-syz*, *-siz* absence. Therefore, even if it is necessary to express these meanings, they are regularly added to the word-former as the ready-made morphemes. This means that the affixes *-çy*, *-çi*, *-ly*, *-li*, *-syz*, *-siz* are regular derivational affixes.

Irregular word-forming affixes do not always participate in the word-formation, they occur in certain words and therefore words formed by irregular derivational affixes cannot form a line in the word-formation system and their participation in the creation of a semantic lexical unit becomes known when they are used together with the word-former. But morphemes are also known in the derivative words formed by irregular affixes. An example of this group of derivational affixes is the affixes *-yt*, *-it*, *-ça*, *-çe*, *-myt*, *-mit* in the derivative words *geç-it*, *iç-it*, *boyun-ça*, *al-myt*, *iý-mit*.

To understand in what sense these affixes formed derivative words, it is possible only if they go together with the forming words. Otherwise it is difficult to determine their meaning.

The regularity or irregularity of derivational affixes is based on the synchronic aspect. Irregular affixes are often non-productive. Although not productive, some derivational affixes are used regularly in the language, and derivative words formed with them form a line. An example of this is the set of words formed by adding affixes *-k*, *-ak*, *-ek*, *-yk*, *-ik*: *dola-k*, *gork-ak*, *seç-ek*, *or-ak*, *gol-ak*, *döw-ek*, *saç-ak*, *dara-k*, *aç-yk*, *ýap-yk* and etc.

Differing from English, in Turkmen there are homonymic, synonymic and antonymic derivational affixes [Borjakow A. 1993, sah. 15]. Derivational affixes eventually form lexical units. Such derivative words enter into different relations with each other

in meaning. A unit that creates such homonymic, synonymic, and antonymic relationships can be associated with derivational affixes. Unlike lexical homonyms, synonyms, and antonyms related to the semantic side of language facts, word-forming homonymy, antonymy, and synonymy includes not only semantics, but also the structural aspect of derivative units. Like lexical homonyms, homonymic derivational affixes are formally only equivalents of all affixes with different meanings that do not have semantically related meanings. For example, even if the derivational affix *-y, -i* phonetically similar in the derivative words *guty, öri, dañy and synpy, taryhy, emeli* derivational affixes in these two derivative groups of words is different affixes that have external similarities in the origin and significance of word-formation. The affix *-y, -i* in the words *guty, öri, dañy* is an affix of the noun, and the affix *-y, -i* in the derivative words *synpy, taryhy, emeli* is adjective forming and by origin is used mainly in the derivative words.

Synonymous units of the language were mainly studied in the vocabulary. Derivational affixes are used to enrich the vocabulary of a language by forming new words. However, it is quite natural that such derivative words can be synonymous to each other. When derivational affixes form synonymous relationships, the words to which they are added are similar, and the derivational affixes added to them are different. As a result, the synonymy of the derivative word formed by adding other derivational affix is directly related to the derivational affix. For example, the affixes *-ly, -li* and *-dar* in the synonyms *bergili – bergidar, algyly – algydar*, as well as *-ly, -li* and *-dan, -kär* in the similar adjectives *gadyrly – gadyrdan, günäli – günäkär* are quite different derivational affixes, but words formed by adding them form a number of synonyms. Synonymy of words that make up this derivative synonymous series is based on the derivational affixes [Borjakow A. 1993, sah.16].

Usually antonyms, i.e. words with the opposite meaning, are studied in the vocabulary. We can determine how and in what way antonyms participate in words with opposite lexical meanings, and on this basis recognize that each of the words and derivational affixes has the opposite meaning. For example, the antonymic relations of such words as *ak – gara, dok – aç, gel – git, aç – ýap, öň – soň, ir – giç, köne – täze, ýagşy – ýaman* are shown in the lexical meaning of the words themselves. But in the derivative words *akylly – akylsyz, işli – işsiz* the relation with the opposite meaning becomes clear together with the meaning of the derivational affixes *-ly, -li and -syz, -siz* [Baýjanow B. 2016, sah. 76]. But the occurrence of derivational affixes in antonymic relations is very limited in comparison with homonymic, synonymic derivational affixes.

Antonymous series of derivational affixes also refers to lexical antonyms. In this case, the lexical meaning of the non-derivative word is added to the antonymic relation with the meaning of the derivational affix in the set of derivative words. An example of this is the antonymic relationship between the word and derivative word from the original word in antonyms such as *dogry – nädogry, ynsap – biynsap, hak – nähak, mert – namart, asyl – bedasyl*. It is known that derivational affixes generate antonymic relations.

In English there are minor types of modern word-formation, i.e. **shortening, blending, acronymy, sound interchange, sound imitation, distinctive stress, and back-formation** [ЗЫКОВА И.В. 2008, с. 70].

Shortening is the formation of a word by cutting off a part of the word. According to the part of the word that is cut off (initial, middle or final) there are the following types of shortenings: 1) initial (or aphaesis). e.g. *fend* (v) < *defend*, *phone* < *telephone*; 2) medial (or syncope), e.g. *specs* < *spectacles*, *fancy* < *fantasy*; 3) final (or apocope), e.g. *ad*, *advert* < *advertisement*, *veg* < *vegetables*; 4) both initial and final, e.g. *flu* < *influenza*, *fridge* < *refrigerator*.

Blending is the formation of a new word by combining parts of two words. Blends may be of two types: 1) additive type that may be transformed into a phrase consisting of complete stems combined by the conjunction and, e.g. *smog* – *sm(oke)* and *(f)og*; 2) restrictive type that can be transformed into a phrase, the first element of which serves as a modifier for the second, e.g.: *telecast* – *television broadcast*.

Acronymy (or graphical abbreviation) is the formation of a word from the initial letters of a word combination. There are two basic types of acronyms: 1) acronyms which are read as ordinary English words, e.g. *UNESCO* [*ju: 'neskəv*] – *the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization*; 2) acronyms with the alphabetic reading, e.g. *BBC* [*'bi: 'bi: 'si:]* – *the British Broadcasting Corporation*.

Sound-interchange is the formation of a word due to an alteration in the phonemic composition of its root. Sound-interchange falls into two groups: 1) vowel-interchange (or ablaut): *food* – *to feed*. In some cases, vowel-interchange is combined with suffixation: *strong* – *strength*, 2) consonant-interchange: *advice* – *to advise*. Consonant-interchange and vowel-interchange may be combined together, *life* – *to live*.

Sound imitation (or onomatopoeia) is the naming of an action or a thing by a more or less exact reproduction of the sound associated with it. cf.: *cock-a-doodle-do*. Semantically, according to the source sound, many onomatopoeic words fall into a few very definite groups: 1) words denoting sounds produced by human beings in the process of communication or expressing their feelings, e.g. *chatter*, *babble*; 2) words denoting sounds produced by animals, birds, insects, e.g. *moo*, *croak*, *buzz*; 3) words imitating the sound of water, the noise of metallic things, a forceful motion, movements, e.g. *splash*, *clink*, *whip*, *swing*.

Back-formation is the formation of a new word by subtracting a real or supposed suffix from the existing words. The process is based on analogy. For example, the word *to butle* «to act or serve as a butler» is derived by subtraction of *-er* from a supposedly verbal stem in the noun *butler*.

Distinctive stress is the formation of a word by means of the shift of the stress in the source word, cf: *'increase* (noun) – *in 'crease* (verb), *'absent* (adj) – *ab 'sent* (v).

Conclusion

In conclusion we can say that there are some similarities and differences between the ways of word-formation in English and Turkmen. It is the universal feature for both

compared languages that word formation is the system of derivative types of words and the process of creating new words from the material available in the language after certain structural and semantic formulas and patterns. In English and Turkmen the words can be formed with the help of affixation, conversion and word-composition. But in English the ways of word-formation differ from those of Turkmen by the existence of minor types of modern word-formation. In Turkmen the ways of word formation differ from those of English by the absence of the minor types of word formation and classification of derivative affixes. In Turkmen there are simple and complex affixes, regular and irregular affixes and homonymic, synonymic and antonymic affixes.

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